

THE DEVELOPMENT OF A SET OF LOW-INFERENCE CODES FOR UNCOVERING STUDENTS' UNDERSTANDING OF LINEAR EQUATIONS: FACILITATING COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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In this paper, our goal is to present a methodological contribution to the analysis of students' linear equation solving competence. While other studies have employed a variety of frameworks for analysing students' understanding of this important topic, none have been able to distinguished between solutions based on 'doing the same to both sides', 'swapping the side swapping the sign' or both. Here we describe the development of a set of low-inference codes that facilitate not only this distinction but also the analysis of their interactions. By way of example, data derived from first year primary teacher education students from a large Swedish university are analysed. The results confirm the framework's ease of operation and its propensity for uncovering the complex understandings students have of this important transitional topic. Some implications for cross-cultural studies of students' equations-related knowledge are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Linear equations, typically construed as one of the most important topics of school mathematics, by providing a meaningful context for students' use of symbols (Brizuela & Schliemann, 2004) offers a strong entry into algebra (Arcavi, 2004). It connects arithmetic to the symbolism of formal mathematics and acts as a *gatekeeper* between school mathematics and higher education and employment (Knuth, Stephens, McNeil, & Alibali, 2006). The literature on equation solving typically distinguishes between two forms of equation. The first, arithmetical equations (Filloy & Rojano, 1989), incorporates the unknown on one side of the equation only. The second, algebraic equations (Andrews & Sayers, 2012), comprises equations with the unknown on both sides. This distinction is didactically significant. On the one hand, an arithmetical equation like $3x + 1 = 13$ can be solved efficiently by means of a straightforward series of operation reversals (Herscovics & Linchevski, 1994). However, if children's first exposure to linear equations is through arithmetical equations then they may face difficulties when faced with algebraic equations like $x + 5 = 4x - 1$ that cannot be solved in such ways. On the other hand, students whose first exposure is to algebraic equations may have an advantage as they will not have learnt a set of procedures that may be superseded.

Historically, algebraic equations have been solved by one of two methods, derived from Viète and Euler respectively (Filloy & Rojano, 1989). The former, warranting a 'swap the side swap the sign' (SSSS) procedure, is based on the transposition of terms from one side of the equation to the other. The latter, justifying a 'do the same to both sides' (DSBS) procedure, draws on operations performed on both sides of the equation simultaneously. Interestingly, intervention studies have typically promoted the balance scale to warrant a DSBS procedure (Caglayan & Olive, 2010; Vlassis, 2002), while analyses of teachers' preferred approaches have found the balance scale being employed with algebraic equations across Europe

(Andrews & Sayers, 2012). In short, the balance scale, despite criticisms (Lima & Tall, 2008), seems positively viewed by both teachers and researchers.

ASSESSING STUDENTS' EQUATIONS-RELATED KNOWLEDGE

Despite this didactical consensus, the limited assessments of students' equation solving have typically found an SSSS procedure (Huntley, Marcus, Kahan & Miller, 2007). Such an approach, reflecting a rote-learned and arbitrary transposition whereby the unknown finishes on the left-hand side and a value on the right (Fillooy & Rojano, 1989), not only perpetuates an operational conception of the equals sign but fails to support students' understanding that such movement does not change the equation's equality. It masks mathematical understanding (Star & Seifert, 2006), and frequently leads to a variety of later difficulties. It is, for many students, a 'magical' (Lima & Tall, 2008) procedure that frequently reduces students "to performing meaningless operations on symbols they do not understand" (Herscovics & Linchevski, 1994, p. 60). Even teacher education students, who may be expected to have a better developed understanding of equations than school students, typically offer solutions indicative of an incomplete understanding of their conceptual basis (Andrews & Xenofontos, 2017; Isik & Kar, 2012). In short, internationally, primary teacher education students have an underdeveloped conceptual understanding of algebra in general and equations in particular, frequently seeing algebra "as a school subject matter dominated by symbols and symbol manipulation" (Stephens, 2008, p. 44).

Procedurally, it is surprising how little attention has been given to the processes that students invoke when solving linear equations. For example, international tests of achievement like PISA and TIMSS typically score correct answer only, as do the national tests in Sweden, the site of the research presented here. From the research perspective, a number of studies have examined aspects of secondary students' equation solving competence in various contexts and by means of various analytical frameworks. However, none of these would have distinguished between a solution based on DSBS and one on SSSS (see, for example, Foster, 2018; Star & Seifert, 2006; Vaiyavutjamai & Clements, 2006). In other words, even when students' solutions to linear equations are under scrutiny, little attention has been paid to the underlining conceptualisation of their thinking.

In this paper, we discuss the development and application of a set of low-inference codes for analysing students' solutions of linear equations. Low-inference code are especially suitable for cross-cultural research, not least because they focus on easily-recognised characteristics of the examined phenomenon, and have been particularly useful in cross-cultural analyses of mathematics classroom activity, both from the perspective of learning outcomes (Andrews, 2009a) and the didactical strategies teachers employ (Andrews, 2009b).

THE CURRENT STUDY

The research presented here draws on an earlier study in which Greek and Greek Cypriot primary teacher education students were invited to explain in writing to a friend, who had been absent when such things had been taught in school, a solution to the equation below, which had been presented with no annotations to indicate the hidden solver's thinking.

$$x + 5 = 4x - 1$$

$$5 = 3x - 1$$

$$6 = 3x$$

$$2 = x$$

The scripts from the two cohorts were subjected to a constant comparison analysis and a set of seven codes identified. While space prevents them being discussed in detail, although their labels can be seen in table 1, we believe that five are self-evident and only two need elaboration. In this respect, an explicit objective referred to the need to find the value of the unknown, while an implicit objective referred to the movement of terms in order to get unknowns on one side of the equation and numbers on the other. Importantly, the seven codes proved adequate for identifying similarities and differences in the two cohorts' scripts, highlighting not only these teacher education students' culturally situated perspectives on linear equations (Andrews & Xenofontos, 2017).

Table 1: The original and two iterations of revised codes

Codes from Greek and Cypriot students' texts	First revised codes for Swedish students	Second revision for Swedish students
The student writes something concerning...		
An aware of unknowns	Unchanged from previous	Unchanged from previous
Defining an unknown	Unchanged from previous	Unchanged from previous
An explicit objective	Unchanged from previous	Unchanged from previous
An implicit objective	Unchanged from previous	
		Particular objective
A rote procedure	Changing side changing sign	
		SSSS general
		SSSS additive
		SSSS division
	Doing the same to both sides	
		DSBS general
		DSBS addition
		DSBS division
	Relational understanding	Unchanged from previous
Inverse operations	Unchanged from previous	
An unspecified process	Uncertain approach	Unchanged from previous
		DSBS induced SSSS
	Checks solution	Unchanged from previous

Developing the codes

Returning to the current study, shortly after beginning their programme and before any exposure to mathematics, one complete cohort of undergraduate Swedish primary teacher education students from a large university were invited to complete the same task. The cohort comprised six classes, each of which was visited by the first author, shortly before the end of a mathematics education lecture, and invited to participate. Although few did so, unwilling students left the room for an early coffee break. Those who remained were given a sheet of paper on which was presented the task and instructions. Additional oral instructions clarified the task and participants wrote their response to their absent school-friend on this paper. After this, scripts were read and reread looking for evidence of the codes applied to the original study of Greek and Cypriot students.

First revised coding schedule

As we browsed these new scripts, the inadequacy of the original coding schedule became apparent. The reasons for this were several. Firstly, many Swedish students wrote of doing the same to both sides, a process not mentioned by any of the Greek or Cypriot students. Secondly, other students wrote of swapping the side and swapping the sign, which aligned with the earlier code concerning the use of a rote rule. Thirdly, a number of Swedish students wrote of the equality of the two sides, which was not something mentioned by either of the Greek-speaking groups. Our first attempt at resolving these tensions were to augment rather than redefine the categories. For example, the first set of revised codes can be seen in table 1. Here, five codes remained unchanged, two were minorly modified and three new ones added. These, as can be seen, reflected the hitherto unseen ‘do the same to both sides’, a solution check and, as a consequence of narratives concerning the equality of both sides, a code concerning a relational understanding of the equals sign, which research had indicated was essential for effective equation solving (Knuth et al., 2006).

Second revised coding schedule

However, as we worked with the Swedish scripts, as well as a second set of data obtained from Norwegian teacher education students, a new set of problems emerged. Firstly, while a code framed by words like explicit may be simple to operationalise, not least because the word explicit implies something visible, implicit codes require the inference of something that is not necessarily visible. Thus, it became apparent as we examined the two sets that the need for interpretation made an implicit objective difficult to discern. Thus, while the original explicit objective, with its general goal, was retained, the implicit objective was replaced with a particular objective, whereby the student had written something concerning getting the x alone and, typically, numbers on the other side. Secondly, a broad code pertaining to SSSS failed to distinguish between students who invoked a general principle and those who applied it to a particular example. In similar vein, DSBS without some form of qualification was too broad. Thus, these two codes became three each, according to whether a student wrote a general statement, a statement concerning a particular additive operation or a particular multiplicative operation. Thirdly, the earlier code concerning inverse operations, was removed as it was thought to require levels of inference unlikely to be found in the data. In a

related vein, the earlier code concerning an uncertain approach was frequently observed in relation to the division of 6 by 3, the coefficient of x in the final row of the given solution. On these occasions, whereby it occurred after earlier invocations of an additive DSBS, we concluded that although it was not made explicit it was a derivative of DSBS. This second set of revised codes are summarised in table 1.

Table 2: Working definitions, frequencies and percentages of each code

Code name	The student writes something about...	Absent	Present	%
Mentions unknown	the unknown or variable	128	28	18
Conceptual objective	finding the 'value of x ' (addresses the <i>purpose</i> of equation solving)	96	60	38
Procedural objective	getting x alone or x on one side (addresses the <i>process</i> of equation solving)	68	88	56
SSSS General	the general SSSS movement of objects	147	9	6
SSSS Particular addition	the additive SSSS movement of objects	103	53	34
DSBS General	solving equations by doing the same to both sides in general terms	129	27	17
DSBS General additive	adding to both sides with no reference to the particular objects of the equation	148	8	5
DSBS Particular additive	adding to both sides with reference to the particular objects of the equation	79	77	49
DSBS General division	dividing both sides by the number in front of x	147	9	6
DSBS Particular division	dividing both sides by 3	105	51	33
Unspecified division	dividing by 3; divide 6 by 3 etc., where it's not clear that both sides are divided	104	53	34
Equality of both sides	both sides of the equals sign being equal	118	38	24
Checks solution	checking the solution	136	20	13

Third revised coding schedule

Each time we revised the codes, new tensions emerged as we attempted to apply them to our scripts. Moreover, the more time we went on their development the more obvious it became that unless they were low inference, relying on clear and unambiguous definitions of specific mathematical actions, the more our difficulties would continue. For example, having coded both our Swedish and Norwegian data again, amounting to around 300 students, some ambiguities remained: can we be confident that a student, who had earlier invoked an additive DSBS and was now dividing 6 by 3 had generalised DSBS? Were we clear in our own minds that three forms of objective were not only instantly recognisable but comprehensive? Would

we be able to recognise consistently a definition of an unknown? These, and other questions led us to a third revision of the codes, which can be seen in table 2. Here, each code is defined by an action, leaving no need for inference. For example, there were now two forms of objective defined by distinctive forms of action. Also, the code concerning a relational understanding of the equals sign, which we now believed to require too high levels of inference, was replaced by a code concerning a statement of equality between the two sides. In addition, where once we tried to infer either an inverse operation or a DSBS induced SSSS, a code involving an unspecified division was introduced. Finally, SSSS division, which had been included for the sake of completeness, was deleted. Our discussions led us to conclude that while SSSS addition is an intuitively natural action to express in words, SSSS division is not so intuitively expressed and, as later confirmed by the data, unlikely to occur.

Applying the third set of codes

Of the Swedish students involved in the study, six either left their sheets blank or apologised for their lack of equations-related knowledge. Otherwise, 156 students offered mathematically interpretable responses, the analyses of which can be seen in table 3. If, within a student’s account, the same code was repeated then only one incidence was recorded. Interestingly, analyses of variance indicated that age had no influence on students’ accounts, while Mann-Whitney U-tests showed no influence of gender.

Interactions of low inference codes

Table 4: Cross-tabulation of conceptual objectives against procedural objectives

		Procedural objective		
		Absent	Present	
Conceptual objective	Absent	48	48	96
	Present	20	40	60
		68	88	156

With respect to showing how these codes facilitate a deeper understanding of students’ equations-related knowledge, a series of cross-tabulations were run. Unfortunately, lack of space prevents many being included but the following two examples offer indications as to how the interactions of the codes play out in meaningful ways. Firstly, table 4 shows the interactions of the two objectives. Here we can see, confirming the figures of table 3, that 60 students (38%) wrote something interpretable as a conceptual objective focused on identifying the value of x , while 88 (56%) indicated a procedural objective, typically about getting unknowns on one side or alone. When the two codes were compared, the scripts of 40 students (26%) yielded both conceptual and procedural objectives, indicating, overall, that 108 individual students (69%) wrote something interpretable as a goal for the equation solving process. Secondly, table 5 shows the interaction of the two particular additive strategies based on DSBS and SSSS respectively, with the former coded for 77 scripts (49%) and the latter for 53 (34%). The cross-tabulation presented in table 5 shows only 12 students (8%) writing of both strategies, with 65 (42% of all students) writing uniquely of a DSBS

approach and 41 (26% of all students) writing uniquely of an SSSS strategy. Thus, overall, 118 students (76%) wrote something recognisable as a ‘conventional’ additive approach. Interestingly, students rarely invoked both conceptualisations, typically offering either a DSBS or an SSSS perspective.

Table 5: Cross-tabulation of DSBS particular addition against SSSS particular addition strategies

		DSBS particular addition		
		Absent	Present	
SSSS particular addition	Absent	38	65	103
	Present	41	12	53
		79	77	156

DISCUSSION

In this somewhat atypical paper, we have narrated the process by which a set of low-inference codes were developed for analysing students’ (in this case beginning primary teacher education students) understanding of linear equations. However, our view is that the framework would be applicable to any students and not just adults. Moreover, it does not reflect a hierarchy (Vaiyavutjamai & Clements, 2006) but a set of curriculum-independent and cross-culturally meaningful categories of understanding. From the perspective of the analysis of Swedish teacher education students’ equations-related understanding, several of the categories may be redundant due to low frequencies. However, that does not mean to say they will not be important in later evaluations of the Norwegian data mentioned earlier, Spanish data that have recently been collected or reanalyses of the Greek and Cypriot data.

Importantly, particularly for those students who invoked an additive DSBS, equation solving does not involve a ‘magical’ procedure (Lima & Tall, 2008) involving “meaningless operations on symbols they do not understand” (Herscovics & Linchevski, 1994, p. 60). It is also interesting to note that, compared with their American peers, the Swedish students of this study understood algebra as much more than “a school subject matter dominated by symbols and symbol manipulation” (Stephens, 2008, p. 44). Finally, the two interactions presented above, one based on the two forms of objective and the other the two additive approaches based on DSBS and SSSS respectively, offered an indication of the complexity of students’ understanding, both with respect to their objectives for equation solving and their preferred strategies.

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